

DETERMINATION OF BIOAVAILABILITY OF OMEPRAZOLE CAPSULES

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Relevance. Capsules are solid dosage forms containing one or more active biological substances with or without auxiliary substances, encapsulated in hard or soft gelatin shells, divided into doses, and used for various types of solid drug formulations. Their quality assessment and bioequivalence determination are essential indicators, considering their bioavailability. In vitro methods and tools were used to determine the bioequivalence of capsules.

The 1st volume of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes tests for the fragmentation of capsules in the Pharmaceutical Technological Trials section. Complete fragmentation - capsules are observed to acquire a soft mass state with noticeable remnants of drug content, indicating that the lower surface of the capsule shells, i.e., the non-melting parts, remains intact. These tests are carried out in two ways: A test for capsules of standard size and a B test for capsules of larger size.

To assess the bioequivalence of capsules, omeprazole capsules produced for once-daily dosing at a dose of 20 mg, intended for the prevention and treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers, were tested for fragmentation and dissolution in various states of in vitro methods.

Objective. To compare the bioequivalence (fragmentation and dissolution tests) of omeprazole capsules produced by several manufacturers through in vitro methods.

Methods and procedures. Capsules for fragmentation and dissolution testing were obtained from different manufacturers at the same dose of omeprazole, as specified in the Pharmaceutical Technological Trials section of the Uzbekistan State Pharmacopoeia. Laboratory identification was conducted according to the methods described in the article on the bioequivalence of solid dosage forms.

Results. The results of the fragmentation test showed that in various companies, omeprazole capsules met the requirements of the reference documents in terms of fragmentation time (20 minutes): the original Omez (Doctor Reddis) capsule fragmented within 17 minutes, Omeprazole (Synthesis) within 11 minutes, and Meromezol (Merrimed) within 12 minutes.

The dissolution test was conducted using a dry chamber apparatus. According to the requirements specified in the reference documents, omeprazole capsules should dissolve within 120 minutes in an acidic environment and release at least 75% of the drug content within 45 minutes in a neutral environment. The experimental results showed that when the active substance in omeprazole capsules was determined by potentiometric method, Omez capsules had 95% release, omeprazole capsules had 92%, and Meromezol capsules had 90% release.

Conclusions. The results of comparing the bioequivalence of omeprazole capsules produced by various companies through in vitro methods in terms of fragmentation and dissolution testing met the requirements specified in the reference documents.